

Safety design and evaluation of the GlaxoSmithKline Priorix MMR-RIT vaccine is marred by incompetence, conflicts of interest and will fuel vaccine hesitancy

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Introduction

Klein et al. (1) evaluated the GlaxoSmithKline (GSK) Priorix MMR-RIT vaccine.

Discussion

Vaccine Design Problems

Safety starts with design (2). GSK has learned nothing from the Pandemrix vaccine induced narcolepsy disaster (3–6). The problem in that case was caused by uncontrolled levels of H1N1 nucleoprotein, a non-target antigen in the vaccine.

GSK have introduced numerous non-target antigens in Priorix with no specifications regarding safe amounts that can be present in a vaccine. Priorix MMR-RIT is known to contain residual chick embryo cell culture proteins as well as excipients such as lactose, mannitol and sorbitol (7). Corvelva has confirmed presence of animal proteins such as actin and vimentin in Priorix (8). Lactose was previously found to be contaminated with cow's milk proteins in other products (9). Source of mannitol and sorbitol need to be determined to find what proteins may contaminate those excipients.

Given current World Health Organization (WHO) clean room specifications, vaccines can be contaminated with aeroallergens (10). With a vaccine design that needs reconstitution, it means more aeroallergen contamination at the end-user site during Priorix reconstitution.

Such non-target antigens result in off-target immune responses that cause asthma, life-threatening food allergy and numerous autoimmune disorders such as type 1 diabetes, autism, neuromyelitis optica spectrum disorders (NMOSD) etc.

Even kids know that wounds should be kept clean and free of pathogens. But here we have live viruses being injected into a wound created on purpose (subcutaneous Priorix administration). We have evolved and developed barriers over millions of years to protect the nervous system from viruses. With a subcutaneous injection, all these barriers are destroyed and the live virus is directly introduced to damaged nerves. Encephalitis is therefore a known vaccine injury listed on the vaccine injury table of the Vaccine Injury Compensation Program for the live virus MMR vaccine (11). For every case of encephalitis, how many cases of sub-clinical damage to nerves go unaccounted? Vaccine designers did not even bother to reconsider the route of vaccine administration to address this problem.

The insanity of injecting animal proteins into humans

The verywellhealth.com website teaches consumers that autoimmunity is triggered “If a foreign substance that is similar to a normal body substance enters the body.” (12)

Any school kid knows that animal proteins resemble human proteins. So what is the most common way “a foreign substance that is similar to a normal body substance enters the body.”? Animal protein containing vaccines. We have of course described the exact immunological process involved in autoimmunity induction due to such immunization with homologous xenogeneic antigens (13).

A good safety evaluation would have caught all these design problems

In Klein et al., there is no mention of non-target antigens and any safety evaluation of such components. Safety evaluation must include pre/post vaccination serology measuring sensitization to all these antigens.

At a minimum, safety evaluation should cover the safety of every component of the vaccine. Chick embryo cell culture and cow’s milk contain thousands of proteins that have strong protein sequence homology to human self proteins. When immunized with such proteins, in the presence of live virus that provide innate immune system co-stimulation, the result is numerous autoimmune disorders (14–18). These autoimmune disorders can take years to manifest themselves. The study was limited to only 180 days. The correct way to evaluate safety would include performance of autoimmune serology pre/post vaccination as suggested by Wraith et al (19). But no such evaluation was performed. Immunogenicity of such host cell proteins resulting in autoimmunity is a well known problem in the biologics industry (20).

Comparison against saline placebo would have avoided occlusion of the real reactogenicity profile.

Fueling vaccine hesitancy

Klein et al. evaluated “noninferiority” of MMR-RIT against Merck’s MMR II, a product introduced 40 years ago. Could they have set the bar any lower? The National Institutes of Health (NIH) spends \$40 billion a year on medical research so we can have a vaccine now that is barely “noninferior” to a 40 year old product? This, when Congress has mandated by law that vaccines have to be continuously improved for safety? A law that the Department of Health and Human Services (HHS) has admitted violating for 30 years (21). Would consumers accept automobiles that were safety tested for “noninferiority” against models built 40 years ago?

As Marcia Angell, former editor of the New England Journal of Medicine writes, transparency does not stop the corruption of medical research by pharmaceutical companies (22). So disclosure by Klein et al. about the funding of the study by GSK and in general, funding of the Kaiser Permanente team by numerous vaccine makers, and the dismal safety evaluation they have performed here, will only fuel vaccine hesitancy.

Conclusion

The WHO has identified vaccine hesitancy as a top ten global threat. With such dismal vaccine designs, safety evaluations and rampant conflicts of interest, what else should one expect? Repeated failures by vaccine regulators such as the MHRA (5), EMA (9) and FDA (23) to learn from past mistakes makes it abundantly clear that vaccine regulators are simply not interested in vaccine safety at all.

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